

INTERNATIONAL SEMINAR:

ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling
Approaches

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Edited by:

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24-25 May 2023

Bragança, Portugal

Published in Bragança, Portugal
May, 2023

Title

ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling Approaches: Book of Abstracts

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Printed by

BRINGRÁFICA Indústrias Gráficas, LDA
Rua Arquiteto Viana de Lima, nº 53
5300-678 Bragança

Publisher

Instituto Politécnico de Bragança
Campus de Santa Apolónia
5300-253 Bragança
Portugal

Edition year: 2023

ISBN: 978-972-745-320-7 (Electronic version)

Handle: <http://hdl.handle.net/10198/1787>

URL: <https://esa.ipb.pt/artisanefood-seminar>

Content

Organising Committee	iii
Scientific Committee	iv
Preface	v
Programme	ix
Content.....	1
The ArtiSaneFood Project.....	5
 Keynote Lectures	 7
Antibacterial and Antioxidant Activities of Mediterranean Plant and Industrial Coproducts.....	9
Bioprotective Potential of Autochthonous Lactic Acid Bacteria in Moroccan <i>Jben</i> Cheese and <i>Merguez</i> Sausage	10
Exploitation Pathways of the Microbiome Characterisation of Fermented Foods	11
Conduction of Tailored Challenge Testing Experiments in Artisanal Foods: Data Preparation for Modelling Purposes.....	12
Dynamic Modelling for Ensuring Microbiological Safety of Artisanal Fermented Foods	13
Risk Assessment of Artisanal Food Products: Importance of Monitoring Process Parameters and Microbiological Quality	14
 Session I: Bio-preservatives as agents to ensure quality of artisanal foods.....	 15
Potential of Essential Oils from Eucalyptus, Peppermint and Pine as Food Preservatives.....	17
Using Byproduct Extracts to Improve the Quality of Traditional Meat and Fish Products	18
Evaluation of the Preservative Capacity of <i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>Acephala</i> Extract in a Bakery Product.....	19
Antioxidant Activity of Garlic Powder During Storage.....	20
Extraction Optimisation of Phenolic Compounds through Response Surface Methodology from <i>Ficus carica</i> L. Leaves and Bioactive Evaluation.....	21

Session: e-Poster flash presentations	23
Stability Studies of Chestnut Flower-Based Ingredient Prospecting Incorporation into Beverages	25
Impact of the Incorporation of Thyme and Rosemary Essential Oils on the Physicochemical Characteristics of Fresh Cheese	26
Phytochemical Content, Antioxidant and Antibacterial Activities of Grape Marc Extracts from Chardonnay and Syrah Varieties Grown in Tunisia	27
Antimicrobial Potential of <i>Eucalyptus</i> Essential Oils.....	28
Effect of Different Extraction Methods on Hesperidin Content, and in vitro Antioxidant and Antibacterial Activities of Ethanolic Orange By-Products Extracts.....	29
Exploring the Effects of Rosemary and Thyme Essential Oils on Merguez Sausage Fermentation: Physicochemical, Microbiological and Sensory Properties.....	30
Antibacterial and Antioxidant Activities of Methanolic and Decocted Extracts of <i>Salicornia arabica</i> : a Halophyte Plant Growing in Tunis Sebkhha	31
Phytochemical Contents, Antioxidant and Antibacterial Activities of Date Seeds Extracts from Tunisian Deglet Enour variety	32
Phytochemical Content, Antioxidant and Antibacterial Activities of Date Fruit Powder from Deglet Nour Variety.....	33
A Meta-Analysis of the in vitro Inhibitory Effects of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Dairy Products against Food-borne Pathogens	34
Biocontrol of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> CECT 4032 in milk, using bacteriocin-producing strain <i>Enterococcus mundtii</i> A2: contamination time effect	35
Application of Starter Cultures as Nitrite Substitutes in a Traditional Portuguese <i>Chouriço</i>	36
Microbiological and Genetic Study of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> Biofilms after their Transfer to Cooked Ham and Simulated in vitro Digestion	37
Thermal Inactivation Kinetics of <i>Salmonella</i> Typhimurium in <i>Alheira</i> Sausage Batter	38
Effect of Ebeam Irradiation on the Antioxidant and the Antimicrobial Activities of Defatted Freeze Dried Cow and Camel Milk Fractions	39
Effect of Herbal Extracts on the Survival of <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in Goats’ Raw Milk Cheese	40
Exploring the Inhibitory Potential of <i>Capsicum annum</i> Extracts Against <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> and Spoilage Bacteria in Fresh Beef Sausages During Storage	41
Potential Effects of Syrup and Seeds Powder of Tunisian Pomegranate (<i>Punica granatum</i> L.) on Characterisation and Sensory Properties of Camel Milk Yogurt.....	42
Genomic Snapshot of Foodborne Pathogens from Artisanal Food Productions of Animal Origin in the Mediterranean Region: Occurrence, Resistome and Virulome.....	43
Metagenomic Investigation of Artisanal Fermented Meat from the Mediterranean Area	44
Microbiological Hazards Investigation in an Artisanal Salami Production Plant	45

Microbiological Hazards Investigation in an Artisanal Soft Cheese Production Plant over One Year	46
Session 2: Bioprotective lactic acid bacteria in artisanal foods.....	47
Assessment of the Bioprotective Capabilities of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Artisanal <i>Alheira</i> , a Portuguese Fermented Sausage	49
Biocontrol of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in fermented milk by selected <i>Lactocaseibacillus paracasei</i> and effect of citrus peel extract on its survival	50
Meta-Analysis on the Inhibitory Effects of Indigenous Lactic Acid Bacteria Supernatant from Dairy Origin against Foodborne Pathogens.....	51
Exploring the Technological and Safety Properties of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Artisanal Salchichón: in Search for a Novel Starter	52
Effect of Commercial Starter Cultures and Selected Bacteriocinogenic Lactic Acid Bacteria on the Microbiological Quality of Goat <i>jben</i> Cheese	53
Study of the Bioprotective Potential of Three Different Lactic Acid Bacteria Cocktails against <i>L. monocytogenes</i> in Vacuum-Packaged Cold Smoked Rainbow Trout	54
Impact of Commercial Starter Cultures on the Microbiological and Physicochemical Properties of Traditional Merguez Sausages	55
Effect of the Drying Process and Incorporation of Natural Preservatives in the Viability of Lactic Acid Bacteria in Yogurts.....	56
Session 3: The microbiome of fermented foods.....	57
Genomic and Phenotypic Analysis of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from <i>Alheira</i> , a Portuguese Traditional Fermented Sausage.....	59
Integration of Contributing Factors Affecting Microbiological Diversity and Food Safety throughout the Artisanal Salchichón Manufacturing	60
Phylogenetic Analysis of Lactic Acid Bacteria species from Cheese: a Comparison between Taxonomy and Physicochemical Characteristics.....	61
Safety Evaluation of Lactic Acid Bacteria and its Bacteriocin Production Based on Whole Genome Sequencing	62
Biofilm-forming Ability of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> and <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> strains isolated from Artisanal Fermented Products Processing	63
Session 4: Predictive modelling in artisanal foods.....	65
Estimation of Growth Parameters of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> under Different Conditions of Mexican Oregano Essential Oil (<i>Poliomintha longiflora</i> Gray), pH and NaCl	67

Assessing the Efficacy of Bioactive Mint Extract in Controlling <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> Growth during Fermentation and Drying of Traditional Dried Sausages: a Mathematical Modelling Approach.....	68
Quantifying and Modelling the Bioprotective Effect of <i>Lactobacillus sakei</i> AE127, <i>Lactococcus lactis</i> AE89, and <i>Enterococcus mundtii</i> AE24 Against <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> 7467 on Vacuum-Packed Cold-Smoked Moroccan Trout	69
Omnibus Modelling to Describe the Effects of Thermisation on <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> in Goat’s Raw Milk	70
Oregano Essential Oil and Processing Conditions: A Predictive Model for Effective <i>Salmonella</i> spp. Inactivation in Sausage Medium	71
Microbiological and Physicochemical Quality Categorisation of Artisanally Produced <i>Alheira</i> Fermented Sausages in Northern Portugal	72
Assessing the Impact of Starter Cultures on the Behavior of <i>Salmonella</i> spp. and <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in Dry-Cured Fermented Sausages.....	73
Study of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Traditional Ripened Foods and Their Antagonistic Effect against <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	74
Comparative Study of Hybrid Optimisation Methods in the Extraction of Antioxidant Phytochemicals from Grape Seed (<i>Vitis vinifera</i>)	75
Effect of Mexican Oregano Essential Oil (<i>Poliomintha longiflora</i> Gray) on the Thermal Inactivation of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> : An In vitro essay.....	76
Session 5: Miscellaneous topics on quality of traditional foods	77
Minimising Multi-Pathogen Risk and Costs through Control Measures: an Application Case for Raw Milk Cheese	79
Bio4Drinks Project: the Obtention of Natural Multifunctional Ingredients for the Beverage Industry	80
Evaluation of the Influence of Intrinsic Properties on the Microbiological Quality of Traditional Portuguese <i>Transmontano</i> Hard Cheese made from Raw Goat’s Milk	81
Effect of Chestnut Flower Extract on the Flavour Stability of Craft Beers	82
Physicochemical Properties and Biological Activities of Fermented Camel Milk: A Comparative Study with Fermented Cow Milk.....	83
Magnesium and Manganese Induced Changes in Chemical, Nutritional, Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Properties of Pansy and Viola Edible Flowers	84
Anti-Tumoral Properties of <i>Allium roseum</i> on Breast Cancer Cells	85

Microbiological and Physicochemical Quality Categorisation of Artisanally Produced *Alheira* Fermented Sausages in Northern Portugal

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Alheira is a fermented sausage, non-ready-to-eat, traditionally produced in Northern Portugal. Due to its artisanal production, *alheira* presents high variability in its nutritional, physicochemical, and microbiological composition. Thus, the aim of this study was to characterise the microbiological and physicochemical properties of *alheira* sausages produced by different regional producers; and to evaluate the associations between relevant attributes. Finished products from 16 factories were analysed, for a total of 80 samples. Mesophiles, lactic acid bacteria (LAB on MRS and M17 agar), *Salmonella* spp., *Staphylococcus aureus* and presumptive *Clostridium perfringens* counts, as well as physicochemical properties (pH, water activity (aw), moisture, ash, protein and fat) were determined. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of these variables was performed to construct quality maps. Three significant components were extracted, accounting for 64.7% of data variability. PC1 (29.3% of the data), which is highly correlated with ash, moisture, carbohydrates and protein, and highly but inversely correlated with fat, appears to characterise nutritionally richer sausages. PC2 (18.7%) is strongly correlated with LAB, and negatively with pH, apparently characterising the extent of fermentation. Finally, PC3 (16.7%) is strongly associated with pH and *S. aureus* and more moderately with *C. perfringens*, which likely represents the development of pathogens due to weaker/slower fermentation. The projection of samples in three-dimensional space also allowed the differentiation of three clusters of factories, i.e., three types of sausages: Cluster 1, comprised of 8 factories, presented average values of pH and protein, and lower values of fat, LAB and *S. aureus*, the latter possibly indicating less manipulated sausages during manufacture; Cluster 2, with 3 factories, presented sausages with lower pH values, protein, and *S. aureus* counts, and higher values of fat and LAB; and Cluster 3 (5 factories), with simultaneously high values of LAB, *S. aureus* and pH, indicating higher manipulation of *alheira* during manufacture and ineffective fermentation.

Keywords: Raw sausage; pathogens; pH; food safety; cluster analysis; factorial analysis.

Supporting Funds: The authors are grateful to EU PRIMA programme and the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) for funding the ArtiSaneFood project (PRIMA/0001/2018). The authors are grateful to the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal) for financial support through national funds FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC) to CIMO (UIDB/00690/2020 and UIDP/00690/2020) and SusTEC (LA/P/0007/2020).